

**Guidance and recommendations for
research assessment in SSH:
Lessons learned in the GraspOS project**

Table of contents

02	Introduction
04	Part 1: Guidelines for Open Science-aware assessment in SSH
04	#1 Involving the community
06	#2 Considering values and context
06	#3 Valuing Open Science Practices
08	#4 Prioritising qualitative assessment
10	Part 2: SCOPE Framework in practice – Recommendations for SSH
10	Start with what you Value
12	Context considerations
13	Options for evaluating
15	Probe Deeply
17	Evaluate your evaluation
18	Concluding remarks
19	Other useful resources

Produced by OPERAS Research Infrastructure as an output of the pilot on Social Sciences and Humanities under the GraspOS project. The pilot was led by:

Carol Delmazo - carol.delmazo@operas-eu.org

Fotis Mystakopoulos - fotis.mystakopoulos@operas-eu.org

This content is available under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY 4.0) license. Please cite this document as: Delmazo, C., & Mystakopoulos, F. (2025). Guidance and recommendations for research assessment in SSH: Lessons learned in the GraspOS project. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17951789>

Funded by
the European Union

The GraspOS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe framework programme under grant agreement No. 101095129. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

Introduction

Substantial changes in research assessment reform can be achieved faster when incentives align with the capabilities and potential of open infrastructures. [The European Union](#) recognises that Open Science and responsible research assessment must go hand in hand. For the purpose of this document, we adopt the broad definition of Open Science proposed by [UNESCO](#):

Open science is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community.

The guidance and recommendations described here are the result of a pilot within the three-year [GraspOS Horizon Europe project](#) (2023-2025), which developed an open and trusted federated infrastructure for next-generation research metrics and indicators. GraspOS sought to support policy reforms for Open-Science-aware and responsible assessment across institutional and national levels.

Addressing the SSH Challenge

[OPERAS Research Infrastructure](#) led the pilot devoted to Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). Research assessment in the SSH presents distinct challenges due to its methodological diversity and unique publication practices. Traditional metrics like the Journal Impact Factor or h-index often fail to capture the value and impact of SSH scholarship, which frequently relies on books, non-scholarly literature, and locally oriented publications - many in national

languages and not indexed in major global databases. As a result, SSH scholarship is often undervalued in quantitative assessment processes.

This document offers guidance and recommendations grounded in lessons learned from this pilot aiming at helping research departments, institutions and universities in establishing more equitable forms of research assessment with SSH specificities in mind, especially when evaluating individuals. The first part offers key guidelines for shaping effective, Open-Science-aware assessment that is responsive to SSH particularities. The recommendations provided in the second part are in line with the guidelines. They are a complement for the steps indicated in the [SCOPE Framework for research evaluation](#), tailoring them to SSH. Developed by the INORMS Research Evaluation Group, SCOPE is a practical step-by-step process designed to help conducting research evaluations.

Following SCOPE, and namely its principle “Evaluate with the evaluated,” the SSH Pilot used a Community of Practice and a series of workshops to involve the community. The exercises brought together several scholars: information specialists, PhD students, early-career and senior researchers from across Europe. Their thoughts and experiences reinforce the call for assessment systems that balance qualitative insights with the responsible use of metrics, recognising the breadth of SSH contributions and their societal impact. Reform must move beyond narrow indicators to reflect the diversity and real-world relevance of SSH research.

What distinguishes this effort from other existing recommendations is its emphasis on both Open Science and the SSH. By highlighting the specific challenges of SSH research, it demonstrates how Open Science can create new avenues for dialogue and inspire fresh approaches to research assessment reform.

PART 1

Guidelines for Open Science aware assessment in SSH

#1 Involving the community

A successful research assessment reform is a process of cultural and systemic change that requires input from local communities. Think, for example, about the assessment of a SSH department at a university: it should be a different process from the one used for a natural sciences department within the same institution. While reform at the global scale is guided by the declarations and initiatives such as [DORA](#) and [CoARA](#), change at the local level, and how researchers are assessed and rewarded at their places of employment, should be achieved by building mechanisms for bottom-up input, creating space for dialogue and recognising the legitimacy of varied scholarly contributions. Simply put, involve those who are being assessed in the discussion of how they should be assessed. Thus, the first step should be to define whom to invite.

Inviting diverse stakeholders

To effectively ensure that there is equity and participation across all levels of the research environment within an institution or department, we suggest that diverse stakeholders should be invited for the conversations about research assessment. These stakeholders may include:

- **Research Staff:** Including Early-Career Researchers (ECRs), senior researchers, and professors.
- **Research Support Professionals:** librarians, data stewards, institutional repository managers, and information specialists, etc.
- **Research Metrics/Data Analysts:** bibliometricians and dedicated data analysts, etc.
- **Senior Management/Administration:** department heads, vice-rectors, and directors of research labs or institutes, etc.

The list is non-exhaustive, but serves as a sample of potential roles for the workshops. The goal is to ensure a holistic approach, involving individuals from various layers of the university's daily life.

Choosing a framework to facilitate discussions

The discussion on research assessment in this proposed bottom-up approach can take different forms, e.g. workshops, communities of practice. A key lesson we learned in the pilot is the need of using an established framework to create conversations within any organisation that wishes to change how they do assessment. For this purpose, we suggest the SCOPE Framework as a primary reference: it was part of the overall GraspOS project activities and proved to be very useful and effective throughout the organisation of workshops in the SSH pilot experience. SCOPE helps steer the conversation on the crucial aspects of a responsible assessment exercise: understanding the values and the context of the assessment, choosing evaluation options, and raising awareness about potential discrimination or gaming. It also stimulates self-evaluation of the entire assessment process.

As a second reference, we propose the [HumetricsHSS initiative](#) given its specific focus on the SSH domain. Tools like the [open-access workshop kits](#) allow teams to reflect on what matters in their specific context and to design assessment practices accordingly.

Another source of guidance for this type of discussions is the [methodology for creating a workshop](#) produced by the Advocacy Special Interest Group of OPERAS. It includes discussion on key initiatives, approaches to Responsible Research Assessment (RRA), the importance of diverse stakeholders, and a concept sheet to create discussions and actions.

Establish a mandate for change

The proposed bottom-up discussions should be framed as part of a long-term commitment to bring change in research assessment. This can be a [CoARA Action Plan](#), which can be informed by the community input.

Ultimately, reform depends on sustained community involvement, engaging researchers not just as subjects of evaluation, but as co-creators of the systems that govern their work. By embedding these participatory values into institutional processes, we move closer to a research culture that is fairer, more transparent, and better aligned with the missions of our scholarly communities.

#2 Considering values and context

In this guideline, we propose the focus to shift from data-driven efforts, i.e. to evaluate based on the data or metrics accessible, but rather have a value-led and context-led assessment process. A responsible assessment system should begin not with the data that is most easily available, but with a clear definition of the qualities and contributions that are valued in the particular context of an institution.

Our work in the SSH pilot showed that while there may be broad consensus on values at a scientific domain level, translating those values into concrete assessment practices is far more challenging. Institutions often operate within distinct research cultures and methodological traditions, which shape how values are understood and demonstrated. What is prioritised in one institutional context may not be in another. As an example, [the Norwegian Career Assessment Matrix \(NOR-CAM\)](#) model demonstrates how context may shape the use of bibliometrics or peer review in evaluation:

Source:
https://www.uhr.no/en/_f/p3/i86e9ec84-3b3d-48ce-8167-bbae0f507ce8/nor-cam-a-tool-box-for-assessment-and-rewards.pdf

In addition, participants needed to understand whether we were talking about individual assessment, or a broader one, e.g., at the departmental level or at the institutional level.

		Country	HEI	Group	Individual
Analysis	To understand	Low impact	Low impact	Medium impact	Medium impact
Advocacy	To show off	Low impact	Low impact	Medium impact	Medium impact
Accountability	To monitor	Low impact	Medium impact	Medium impact	High impact
Acclaim	To benchmark	Medium impact	High impact	High impact	High impact
Adaptation	To incentivise	Medium impact	High impact	High impact	High impact
Allocation	To reward	High impact	High impact	High impact	High impact

Legend:
■ Low impact
■ Medium impact
■ High impact

Source:
<https://inorms.net/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/21655-scope-guide-v10.pdf>

Values and **Context** are interlinked and must be examined as a necessary background for research assessment. We will go into more detail in part 2 of this document (recommendations), given that the first two steps in the SCOPE Framework are precisely to start with values and consider the context of the assessment.

#3 Valuing Open Science Practices

A reform of research assessment that is open-science-aware is about valuing the production, sharing and dissemination of knowledge with transparency and integrity. Open Science practices remain undervalued in research assessment, despite being mentioned in official criteria. Open Science outputs and activities (e.g., data sharing, open peer review) should be part of each institutional evaluation framework, and establishing monitoring mechanisms to track and report them is also essential. Training assessment panels' experts is another pillar: they need knowledge and tools to recognise and reward Open Science contributions and should also be aware of limitations and risks (i.e. creating a new set of quantitative criteria).

Openness and a broader range of outputs

SSH research produces a wide range of valuable outputs beyond journal articles, including monographs, datasets, software, exhibitions, and community-oriented formats in multiple languages. As a consequence, recognition should extend to innovative, accessible formats and multilingual works, ensuring that they are valued not only for their openness but mainly assessed for quality and relevance. A longer list of outputs and activities is available in the recommendations in part 2, since the third step in the SCOPE workflow is precisely to assess the options for evaluation. Making this diversity visible in the research assessment process, together with strengthened qualitative approaches, ensures that evaluations reflect the full scope of academic contributions and value the openness appropriately. A useful example in this direction has been produced by a CoARA Boost project, TREASURE, on [how to better assess and reward open practices and outputs](#), in particular the section “List of practices and outputs + criteria”.

Open infrastructures for responsible assessment

Open infrastructures include a range of resources, offering a more representative and Open Science-friendly way to showcase the work of researchers. These tools and platforms can provide support for the monitoring and assessment of Open Science practices. Examples include [BIP! Scholar](#), which displays various indicators for showcasing researchers’ work and also allows them to write narrative CVs; [OpenAIRE Monitor](#), which provides tailored dashboards and interactive visualisations for monitoring research in various contexts, e.g. at the institutional level; and

[GoTriple](#), which is a multilingual discovery platform bringing into focus diverse outputs produced at the SSH scientific domain. These platforms are part of the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#), where other tools, data and services are also available.

Build capacity for expert assessment with Open Science principles in mind

Evaluating Open Science appropriately requires training on identifying Open Science contributions and rewarding transparency, integrity and the quality of the work. In addition, evaluators need to acknowledge multilingual contributions and other cultural sensitivities as part of the assessment process. A starting point for this process can be a SCOPE+i guide produced by GraspOS that focuses on [how to introduce assessment for Open Science](#).

An important part of this capacity building process is to be aware of some risks and try to mitigate them. Clear definitions, trusted sources, and verification processes are the bases to prevent exploitation of the system. In the recommendations in part 2, we further develop the topic of risks’ mitigation and guarding against gaming, given that the final steps in SCOPE are to probe deeply and evaluate the evaluation.

#4 Prioritising qualitative assessment

During the pilot, the concept of qualitative assessment was discussed. The SSH community clearly emphasised its value, especially when assessing individuals. Participants repeatedly highlighted that quality cannot be reduced to numbers, nor captured through indicators or journal-based proxies. Instead, understanding research quality requires looking at how researchers' work is produced: research process, methods, openness, data, analysis and the broader context in which their contributions take shape. This aligns closely with the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, where quality is linked with integrity. What emerged in our discussions is that qualitative assessment is a fundamentally human endeavour, and there is no substitute for human judgement. Below we summarise the key messages derived from these discussions and offer practical suggestions for implementing qualitative approaches.

Prioritise qualitative criteria at the level of the individual assessment

Our group was unanimous that when assessment applies to a person, qualitative assessment becomes central. The broader the scale of evaluation, the more quantitative elements may enter

Approach quality as a multi-aspect rooted in human judgement

Neither journal articles nor quantitative counts of outputs can fully represent quality. No single measure can capture the richness and complexity of a researcher's work. It remains an interpretative activity requiring careful, human evaluation.

Place peer review at the centre of quality assessment

CoARA emphasises [qualitative assessment primarily through peer review](#). Our guideline reaffirms this understanding of how quality should be assessed, as peer review enables evaluators to consider, in line with Open Science principles, diverse aspects such as methodological rigour, data quality and the broader impact of the research. Ultimately, this approach supports integrity, robustness and responsible research practices.

Adopt narrative CVs within assessment practices

The narrative CV allows researchers to provide context and explain their contributions. It was widely recognised in the pilot as central for obtaining a fuller picture of a researcher, especially in SSH. To support this, the pilot produced [a template](#) built on the well established Resumé for Researchers of the Royal Society, changing the modules' description to address SSH nuances.

From the Guidelines to the Recommendations

The first part offered guidelines as pathways for shaping effective, Open-Science-aware assessment that is responsive to SSH particularities. The following recommendations, presented in **Part 2 - SCOPE Framework in practice – Recommendations for SSH**, are designed to flow directly from and reinforce those guidelines, specifically complementing the steps indicated in the **SCOPE Framework for research evaluation**, tailoring them to the SSH domain.

PART 2

SCOPE Framework in practice Recommendations for SSH

The following recommendations focus on how to apply the unique elements of **SCOPE** in SSH contexts:

Start with what you value

From the SCOPE Framework: "Begin the evaluation by stating your personal values about the subject, avoiding external influences or relying solely on available data resources to prevent the "Streetlight Effect".

Specific recommendation for SSH: Ensure that key organisational values in the research assessment process are aligned with the SSH context.

Embodying the recommendation: the SSH Pilot experience

The community was invited to discuss and refine what should be valued in an assessment process for SSH research. The starting point was a set of values defined in internal discussions within the GraspOS project prior to the workshops. Three super-values were proposed: transparency, output diversity, and quality.

Workshops' participants offered several refinements and additional super-values:

- **"Transparency"** was generally well-received, but caution was advised regarding its definition and practical application, with discussions differentiating it from "openness". Thus, **"Openness"** was suggested as a super-value itself, encompassing the idea of Open Science and the challenges it faces in various SSH fields.
- **"Output diversity"** was debated, and the suggestion was to simply use **"Diversity"** as a super value, to encompass broader concepts like languages and career positions, rather than just outputs.
- **"Quality"** was acknowledged as a crucial value, although the difficulty of its measurability was also highlighted.
- **"Interdisciplinary collaboration"** was proposed as another super-value, especially in interdisciplinary institutes.
- **"Collegiality"** was another one proposed, to value teamwork and practices such as mentoring younger scholars.

The exercises clearly showed that the set of super-values can vary depending on the institution: while all can be guiding concepts for the SSH domain as whole, the super-values must be prioritised to suit each specific institutional context.

The super-values should, then, manifest into a value statement. The proposed statement was:

- **"Inclusivity of diverse outputs and practices".**

Participants expressed mixed feelings about it. Some noted that it seemed to omit quality, which they considered even more important than diversity, though they also admitted that "quality" is difficult to frame as a value in itself. Participants considered that the statement works as a guiding principle, "good enough" for the level of the exercise, since it emphasised inclusivity without being overly prescriptive. This step was valuable because it led to the synthesis of broader values into a single, concise statement that can effectively guide the evaluation.

The final step was to discuss the sub-values, which are related to more granular issues to be considered in research assessment. Participants assessed the sub-values pre-defined in the GraspOS internal discussion: Widen the scope of research outputs; Raise the profile of publication practices; Create assessment protocols that respect diversity of outputs and practices; Provide support in the use of services that enable SSH monitoring. In an exercise to refine the sub-values, they suggested the following formulations:

- **Going beyond measurable / tangible outputs** to include community engagement and transdisciplinary research practices.
- **Publishing less, not more,** and considering the individual's role in research processes.
- Moving away from "bean counting" towards **evaluating plans and goals.**
- Implementing **"evaluation to the top"**, where researchers can report what was missed or lacking from superiors or institutions to achieve their goals.

Again, the sub-values will depend on the specific context of the institution in charge of the assessment. These are examples on how initial statements can be developed if discussed with the community.

Our pilot did not attempt to define or impose a universal set of overarching values. Rather, this case study reminds us of the importance of holding dialogues at the local level and engaging directly with researchers to understand their interpretations and priorities in terms of what is valued within a research environment and so that individuals are assessed accordingly.

Context Considerations

From the SCOPE Framework: "Consider the context in the evaluation by focusing on the specifics: identify who you are evaluating (considering entity size and discipline) and why you are conducting the evaluation.

Specific recommendation for SSH: Consider the context of SSH practices in the evaluation

Embodying the recommendation: the SSH Pilot experience

The SCOPE Framework highlights the importance of situating the evaluation within its proper context. In our pilot, this principle was underscored by the heterogeneous nature of the participants' background and institutions, highlighting that what counts as valuable, feasible, or fair in one setting may not translate directly into another.

As stated in the guideline #2 in Part 1, evaluation criteria depend heavily on the level of assessment: what is relevant for the assessment of an individual may differ substantially from an evaluation focused on departmental, institutional, national, or project levels. Second, the purpose of evaluation also dictates what is valued, whether it is yearly appraisal, career progression, benchmarking, promotion, or a funding application. These considerations apply to all research domains but are particularly important for framing discussions in SSH.

Context considerations applying across all scientific domains:

Evaluation criteria vary by level (individual, departmental, institutional, national, project).

The **purpose** of evaluation (appraisal, promotion, funding, benchmarking) dictates what is valued.

Alongside these two dimensions (level and purpose) of assessment across all domains, the SSH pilot highlighted three other specific dimensions to take into consideration. First, citation behavior and publication practices in SSH diverge from STEM. Citation accumulation follows a different trajectory from the outset, and publication formats are more diverse, i.e. heavily favouring books. In addition, since local relevance is key, internationalisation becomes less critical. Second, the definition of Open Science is context-dependent: what constitutes 'open data' in STEM does not translate directly to SSH disciplines, where qualitative data, such as interviews or participatory research, presents distinct ethical challenges for sharing. Third, the language of publication is a decisive factor. Many SSH researchers publish in local languages, often resulting in their absence from international indexes and reduced visibility in global evaluation systems.

SSH-specific context considerations:

Domain differences in citation behaviour, outputs (e.g. books), and local relevance.

Open Science interpreted differently: e.g. "open data" in STEM \neq research materials in history, literature, or qualitative studies.

Language and venue of publication: many SSH outputs are published in local languages or journals not indexed internationally.

Evaluation systems that take into account both the broad dimensions of research and the context specificities of SSH are more likely to be effective, inclusive, and supportive of SSH researchers.

Options for Evaluating

From the SCOPE Framework: "When evaluating, explore both quantitative and qualitative options. Exercise caution when using quantities to represent qualities.

Specific recommendation for SSH: Expand evaluation options to ensure fair recognition of diverse outputs and activities in SSH assessment.

Embodying the recommendation: the SSH Pilot experience

The SCOPE Framework stresses that evaluation must consider a range of options, methods, and indicators, rather than defaulting to a narrow set of quantitative measures. In the SSH pilot, this principle was central: participants consistently highlighted the limitations of traditional bibliometrics and explored more inclusive approaches that better reflect SSH scholarship.

Current research assessment systems for SSH still rely heavily on traditional metrics that have been strongly criticised. Specifically, the h-index and its derivatives were highlighted as inappropriate, and the Journal Impact Factor (JIF) was deemed unsuitable, especially in the Humanities where citation practices have different characteristics from STEM, such as longer timescales for citation accumulation. Consequently, the continued emphasis on publishing in high-ranking journals is problematic. Participants also strongly

criticised the 'counting beans' mentality, where sheer numbers of committee participation, awards, or grant acquisition substitute for deeper, qualitative evaluation. To move the focus away from journal metrics, we propose a more diversified portfolio of outputs and activities based on the pilot discussions. The more we expand this list, the more we move towards qualitative assessment process.

Diverse scholarly outputs: monographs, books, preprints, multilingual publications, datasets, software, games, artwork, catalogues, zines, exhibitions, cultural object digitisation, and more.

Data Management Plans: suggested as a potential indicator for reproducibility and documentation, particularly if tied to open licensing. However, the evaluation of DMPs shouldn't be only quantitative.

Varied activities: peer review (highlighted as a crucial qualitative indicator); participation in editorial duties, advisory boards, proposal development, or research projects; teaching and supervision (mentoring, quality of guidance, open educational resources).

Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT): recognising the breadth of contributions beyond authorship, from data curation and editing to translation and project delivery.

Interdisciplinary Collaborations: recognising the effort to establish collaborations, especially between SSH and STEM or across SSH subfields.

Societal engagement: collaborations with policymakers, NGOs, and cultural institutions, science communication to diverse audiences, and participatory research.

This is not an exhaustive list, but it showcases key elements mentioned in the discussions. Crucially, those outputs should be assessed and evaluated using human judgement by means of peer review.

From our perspective, the diversity of outputs can also be supported by infrastructures for a more nuanced research assessment. In line with guideline #4 from Part 1, Narrative CVs were strongly advocated as a qualitative alternative to conventional CVs, allowing researchers to explain their career path, contributions, and societal impact in a storytelling format.

To test the [Narrative CV designed with SSH particularities](#) within the pilot, we partnered with the BIP! Scholar platform, which is part of the GraspOS infrastructure. Participants pointed out as positive the platform's capacity to build researcher profiles enriched with contextual information and [open indicators](#), moving beyond conventional metrics. Outside of the project's infrastructure, the [PEP-CV platform](#) is a useful example of the growing environment supporting the development of narrative CVs.

Monitoring dashboards, such as the [OpenAIRE Monitor](#), were discussed as models of infrastructure supporting assessment. When it comes to books, [OPERAS Metrics](#) is a valuable tool to assess their impact, and the [Peer Review Information Service for Monographs \(PRISM\)](#) contributes to the transparency of assessment practices around books.

Taken together, these discussions call for a plurality of methods in SSH research evaluation, methods that reflect the richness of outputs, activities, and infrastructures moving decisively beyond the narrow confines of traditional metrics.

Probe deeply

From the SCOPE Framework: In your evaluation, consider potential discrimination, gaming of the approach, unintended consequences, and weigh the cost-benefit.

Specific recommendation for SSH: Anticipate problems and mitigate risks in SSH research assessment.

Embodying the recommendation: the SSH Pilot experience

The “P” in the SCOPE Framework emphasises the need to actively prevent misuse of evaluation systems, including gaming, discrimination, and structural bias. This is equally important across domains. During the

community consultation process, participants naturally referred to some of these risks when exploring options for evaluating or assessing how to consider Open Science practices, drawing attention to how proposed processes may inadvertently reinforce exclusionary or counterproductive behaviours.

The reliance on easily monitored sources like journal articles risks excluding large areas of SSH scholarship that do not fit traditional or quantifiable models. Simplistic quantitative measures that ignore discipline, language, or career stage are inappropriate for SSH, and “one-size-fits-all” approaches are bound to exclude significant scholarly contributions.

The risk of creating more “bean countings” was voiced repeatedly. There is a significant risk that new metrics become targets, encouraging researchers to maximise outputs for the sake of numbers rather than for quality or genuine engagement. Predatory open access journals were cited as an example of this danger, where researchers may publish simply to meet KPIs, regardless of quality. Similarly, Data Management Plans (DMPs), while potentially useful, were seen as too often reduced to an administrative hurdle, encouraging superficial compliance instead of real improvement. Popularity metrics (e.g., views, downloads) were also noted as problematic: they are vague, often dependent on DOIs, and outputs without a persistent identifier, risk being left out of this category.

Peer review was discussed as key for a qualitative assessment, but participants also highlighted its limitations: inconsistency, lack of standardisation, uneven review quality, and

even emerging risks such as AI-generated reviews undermining credibility.

Participants also drew attention to other systemic constraints such as the institutional hierarchies that can obscure individual contributions and obstruct fair recognition, with senior figures taking disproportionate credit for collective work. Early-career researchers, in particular, face difficulties in demonstrating “impact to society” at their career stage.

Key risks raised:

“Streetlight effect”: measuring what is easy to monitor and ignoring diverse outputs and activities that are not visible to traditional scientific indicators.

New quantitative “bean counting”: encouraging researchers to maximise outputs for the sake of numbers, new KPIs, rather than for quality.

Peer Review challenges: peer review risk being inconsistent, vulnerable to misuse (e.g. AI).

Structural/systemic biases: hierarchies hindering fair recognition; individualistic systems discouraging collaboration.

Having identified the risks, as mitigation strategies, both guidelines and recommendations presented already point to certain strategies that would create mitigation strategies:

To avoid the “Streetlight effect”, it is essential to make sure that the diverse scholarly contributions are fully incorporated into assessment criteria. To enable this, evaluators should have the appropriate disciplinary and methodological expertise, supported by training to ensure they can assess diverse forms of SSH scholarship. Assessment policies must also require justification for any quantitative indicator used, particularly where language, format or disciplinary norms vary. Finally, evaluation must explicitly recognise local relevance and community impact as legitimate dimensions of research quality.

Any assessment system that includes new metrics, must include mechanisms for regular review and adaptation to rapidly identify and disincentivise emerging gaming behaviors, such as publishing in predatory journals. Tools like DMPs should be streamlined to focus on substance and genuine improvement. The evaluation of DMPs should be performed by experts who assess the integrity of the data process.

To address peer review challenges, explicit guidelines should be used to ensure consistency and quality across reviews, potentially involving reviewer training and recalibration sessions. To address the emerging risk of AI-generated reviews, systems must implement robust authenticity checks.

Furthermore, mitigation must target structural and systemic constraints that obscure fair recognition. Assessment panels should be mandated to look beyond institutional hierarchies and evaluate contributions based on

Evaluate your evaluation

From the SCOPE Framework: " Evaluate your evaluation by assessing whether it achieved its goals, considering both formative and summative aspects. Use SCOPE as a framework for evaluating your evaluation."

Specific recommendation for SSH: Evaluate the evaluation systems by engaging SSH communities in feedback and iterating for improvement.

Embodying the recommendation: the SSH Pilot experience

The "E" in the SCOPE Framework asks evaluators to examine their own processes: to reflect on whether the evaluation works as intended, identify its limitations, and determine how it can be improved. Similar to the Probing recommendation, this principle is crucial across all domains. The SSH Pilot of GraspOS, while not an assessment process per se, embraced this principle through community engagement in validation and evaluation workshops. This ensured the outputs of the pilot were rigorously scrutinised and their limitations highlighted.

Moving beyond the confines of the pilot, when creating or improving evaluation practices, it is essential to reflect on whether they achieve their intended objectives. For example, when new scholarly activities are introduced into

assessment, how were they evaluated? Were indicators used responsibly? Was the peer review process robust and carried out by appropriate experts, with attention to structural and systemic biases?

Another example closely connected to the project's philosophy is the integration of Open Science into assessment systems. Evaluating the evaluation involves examining whether SSH researchers understood and embraced this concept and whether they were able to contribute meaningfully to the agreed Open Science activities.

Inevitably, change generates new insights, making iterative improvement a core part of responsible assessment. Therefore, whenever any element in the evaluation process is added or amended, time must be set aside to reflect on whether it has achieved its intended goals.

Concluding remarks

Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) in SSH requires a shift from narrow, metric-driven approaches to value-led, context-sensitive, and community-designed systems that recognise the full diversity of scholarly contributions. This reform is cultural and systemic, rather than merely technical, and is most effective when aligned with Open Science principles and embedded in local institutional realities. This entails balancing qualitative and quantitative elements, maintaining the centrality of expert, peer-based judgement, especially when assessing individuals.

Our contribution is part of a growing list of initiatives of global RRA efforts. While this movement is necessary, the sheer volume of recommendations can create complexity for institutions seeking practical implementation. What distinguishes this specific effort is its deliberate focus on the intersection of Open Science and the unique challenges faced by the SSH domain. Our goal was to provide concrete examples and lessons learned from the GraspOS SSH pilot, and assist departments and universities in establishing more equitable assessment practices. A checklist to help you design a responsible assessment in SSH is [available in Zenodo](#).

It is crucial to acknowledge the inherent limitations of the GraspOS SSH Pilot and this document. The pilot was a community engagement and validation exercise, not an assessment process per se. Therefore, this guidance is based on community input and lessons learned, not the results of an implemented system. Furthermore, the exercises did not attempt to define a universal set of overarching values; instead, they served to remind the community of the critical importance of holding dialogues at the local level. This underscores the document's limitation in prescribing specific actions, as reform is most effective when embedded in local realities.

RRA, particularly when tailored to the complexity of SSH, has a long way to go, and its success depends on sustained community involvement. We believe the dialogue must remain open, building mechanisms for bottom-up input. We sincerely hope that this contribution, with its focus on SSH specificities, Open Science awareness, and practical guidance, proves useful in fostering a fairer, more transparent research culture within the SSH community.

Other useful resources

The GraspOS project has developed a tailored infrastructure that works together with the existing SCOPE Framework, which is known as the SCOPE+i Framework. It consists of two main components: assessment process resources and digital services: [SCOPE+i Framework - GraspOS](#). The catalogue of resources can be accessed here: <https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/catalogue/>.

You can also have a look at the slides and collaborative notes from the GraspOS Community of Practice entitled "The role of Open Science in fostering a more inclusive research assessment process in SSH": <https://zenodo.org/records/10562683>.

Still from the GraspOS project, have a look at the "Deliverable 5.3: Pilot findings and progress report": <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17035609>.

While not directly mentioned in the document, we would like to highlight a parallel effort from a project that explored similar concepts to GraspOS in relation to reforming research assessment. This Output of the [OPUS project](#) brings examples of interventions designed to support and accompany the research assessment processes: https://opusproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/OPUS_D2.1_Interventions_FINAL_PUBLIC.pdf.

The "Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook" produced by the PathOS project is also highly advisable: [Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook](#).

A particularly valuable complementary source is the TREASURE project Deliverable D.2 on reproducible, reusable and open research practices and outputs which provides a list of criteria to assess diverse practices and outputs: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15785597>.

Another key initiative, again from outside the GraspOS project, is related to Narrative CVs: the [recommendations for funders](#) from the Research on Research Institute (RoRI), aiming to establish a better culture for adopting Narrative CVs.

About Open Science Monitoring and the "Streelight effect", we suggest this blog post: <https://www.leidenmadtrics.nl/articles/the-unesco-open-science-outlook-there-is-progress-in-os-but-it-is-unequal>.

graspos
open research assessment dataspace

OPERAS